

Enablers of low-latency immersive interaction in future remote-rendered Mixed Reality applications

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Abstract

Mixed Reality (MR) has launched from science fiction but its entrance in reality can reshape our society. By combining the physical and virtual worlds, it provides novel ways of immersive interactions and experiences and by these means enables a new generation of applications. The most exciting and challenging ones support collaborative, multi-user operation in large geographical scale, require real-time environment comprehension and high visual fidelity. The success or failure is definitely impacted by the capabilities and performance limits of edge cloud platforms and 5G/6G networks providing the offloading features for CPU/GPU intensive MR functions. In addition, the desired quality of user experience calls for further mechanisms at the application level hiding the consequences of varying network characteristics. In this paper, we propose a novel edge cloud based architecture for future remote-rendered MR applications supporting low-latency immersive interactions. Our contribution is threefold. First, the system architecture is presented focusing on the remote rendering, 3D simulation and environment detection control loops. Second, we highlight the main features of our proof-of-concept prototype and our dedicated application, namely the Mixed Reality version of a Rocket League inspired game. Third, the concepts are validated via experiments in a Beyond 5G infrastructure where we analyze the operation and latency characteristics of the overall system. In addition, the quality of the user experience is also evaluated via real-life experiments conducted as part of a student competition. The results show that the latency and jitter characteristics of the most sensitive render loop can be managed efficiently together by a network-level control (slice priorities) and an application-level (dynamic jitter buffer) mechanism.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Mixed / augmented reality.**

Keywords

Human computer interaction (HCI), Mixed Reality, Augmented Reality, immersive applications, edge computing, environment understanding, 5G/6G

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1 Introduction

Mixed Reality (MR) is the youngest member of the Extended Reality (XR) application family. It is a blend of the physical and virtual worlds, creating immersive environments through the use of XR glasses where virtual elements interact with the real world in real-time. These capabilities open the door to a new generation of XR applications in many fields with special societal importance and business potential. Medical/healthcare [1], Industry 4.0/5.0 [9], entertainment and online gaming [22], construction/architecture [5] are just highlighted areas where only low-latency immersive interaction and high visual fidelity can ensure the correct and acceptable operation.

For example, a live, remotely assisted surgery via a head-mounted MR display or a dynamic, personalized billboard attached to a moving vehicle are closer to science fiction today, but might be part of our life tomorrow thanks to the revolutionary MR technologies. The main challenges of these future applications stem from the collaborative, multi-user operation, the resource demand of high visual fidelity and the large-scale environment detection, understanding and comprehension. The latter capability is the key enabler of future MR features. Offloading the CPU/GPU intensive MR functions to the edge cloud infrastructure is a straightforward and inevitable step. For example, by applying remote rendering techniques [11, 13], we can render objects with a much higher polygon count, significantly enhancing visual fidelity. However, the challenging latency, jitter and bandwidth requirements call for novel 5G/6G networking technologies as well in order to keep the different control loops in the appropriate operation regime. But in spite of the promises of future 6G systems, additional techniques are also necessary to overcome the impact of increased latency. For example, recently proposed warp methods are able to distort/adjust the remotely rendered, slightly delayed images in order to follow the changes in headpose or user position (happened after the creation of the frame) just before displaying them. Moreover, sophisticated movement prediction algorithms can mitigate lagging of object tracking functions.

In this paper, we propose a novel edge cloud based architecture for future MR applications enabling low-latency immersive interaction in remote-rendered virtual spaces combined with physical environments. Our contribution is threefold. First, the system architecture is presented focusing on the main control loops, namely the remote rendering, the 3D simulation and the environment detection loops. These control mechanisms show different operation characteristics and require distinct capabilities and performance from the underlying network and edge cloud infrastructure. In addition, they directly affect the user experience. Second, we highlight our proof-of-concept prototype implementing the key elements of the proposed architecture. A special application is also delivered that poses substantial challenges to the system and the underlying infrastructure. It is the Mixed Reality version of a Rocket League [15] (car soccer) inspired game. Third, we analyze the operation and latency characteristics of the overall system in a Beyond 5G (B5G) infrastructure, including network and edge resources. Besides the quantitative validation, the concepts are also evaluated via real-life experiments conducted as part of a student competition where the quality of the user experience is analyzed.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Sec. 2, the main challenges of immersive interaction in MR applications are highlighted and the related state-of-the-art solutions are summarized. Sec. 3 is devoted to our proposed architecture and its key features. A proof-of-concept embodiment of this architecture and a test application are presented in Sec. 4. The measurement environment and the main results of the evaluation are presented in Sec. 5 and Sec. 6, respectively. And finally, Sec. 7 concludes the paper.

2 Immersive interactions: challenges

In this section, we identify and analyze the main challenges of immersive interactions in MR applications and also highlight related solutions which partially address these problems.

2.1 Low-latency interaction

It is evident that the sensitivity to latency varies for different types of interactions in MR applications [2]. Anyone who used e.g. HoloLens 2 noticed that grabbed objects follow the user's hand with a slight delay, but this constant delay does not degrade the user experience. If the interaction is driven by e.g. the number of people in a store, the latency requirement of that detection function is typically not so strict. In contrast, if a virtual ball bounces back with a delay from a physical wall, it distorts the image and impairs the user experience. Similarly, in a ping-pong application, where we hold a controller, our virtual racket must be precisely in the position of that controller. Obviously, in the latter examples, latency is critical and cannot be tolerated. As a consequence, we can distinguish between moderate and the much more challenging low-latency interactions based on how their processing time affects the user experience.

Mixed reality systems are still far from perfectly integrating life-like virtual objects into physical space. There are several reasons for this. One of them is the quality of the rendered image, as current headsets are unable to render high-polygon-count objects in real-time due to lack of sufficient computing capacity, making the

appearance of virtual objects less realistic. To address this issue, remote rendering systems have been developed, where the rendering task is offloaded from the devices to powerful servers running in the cloud or at the edge. Such solutions are Nvidia CloudXR [13] and Microsoft Azure Remote Rendering [11]. Although the image quality improves with remote rendering, a delay is added to the system, which raises extra challenges in terms of immersive interactions. While the image is rendered for the current frame, the user can move (even in case of local rendering). This very slight movements can cause that our brain perceives we are not seeing the intended image. Over time, this discrepancy can lead to motion sickness. To mitigate these issues, remote rendering systems often use warp techniques, primarily time warp [24] and space warp [28], to ensure that the streamed image stays in sync with the user's movements and to prevent potential image loss from degrading the user experience. During time warp algorithms, the incoming image is slightly adjusted based on the user's position changes that occur during the operation time of the render loop. However, time warp cannot function effectively if the latency is too high. The utilization of space warp eliminates the need for rendering every frame. Instead, every other frame is generated on the client side by leveraging the previous frame and motion vector data. This technology is particularly beneficial in remote rendering systems, as it optimizes bandwidth usage by allowing interpolated frames to be locally generated on the client, thereby reducing the volume of transmitted data. Furthermore, it enhances the user experience in scenarios with unstable network connections by compensating for missing frames, ensuring smoother visual continuity.

2.2 Static vs. dynamic environments

The level of challenge is greatly impacted by the characteristics of the surrounding physical environment, i.e., whether there are static or dynamically changing objects within the application. If we only want to display a virtual object at a specific point, its placement and rendering depend solely on the device, a task easily accomplished by modern headsets equipped with multiple sensors and cameras. However, when these objects are in motion, perhaps bouncing off physical objects or following them, we are dealing with a considerably more challenging task that significantly burdens the devices. Moreover, if the semantic understanding of the environment is also intended, the task's complexity and its resource demand (e.g. GPU and memory for handling large AI models) will be much higher, making it evident that environment detection and tracking can easily be a bottleneck in MR applications.

Object detection in static environments and combined object detection and tracking are (will be) crucial in modern (future) MR services. However, the devices can only recognize simple surfaces by default. It is possible to run object detection on them, for example, by using the Unity Barracuda solution [23] or by incorporating YOLO [12]. The advantage of these solutions is that they are fast when we only want to detect a few objects, but their disadvantage is that they take a significant amount of resources from devices that are usually resource-poor anyway, and they cannot provide adequate performance when running complex models [8].

Offloading these tasks to cloud/edge servers is a solution that allows complex models as well. However, the introduced extra

latency is a serious drawback to be mitigated with low-latency network protocol [6], or the use of dedicated hardware acceleration in the cloud/edge (e.g.: GPU), which in many cases provides a significant advantage. Another benefit is that we can extract further information from the dispatched image. With the help of innovative AI technologies, we can even determine material properties, which can further improve visual fidelity. For instance, a virtual ball would bounce differently off concrete than off sand. Furthermore, device (which is usually a mobile device with a finite energy supply) energy usage can be reduced by outsourcing compute-heavy tasks [29].

In a dynamic environment, object detection alone is not sufficient, as objects can move, so we also need to apply object tracking. ARKit [3] has developed a solution for this, but currently, it updates the object's position very slowly, more like sequential detections. VisionLib's solution [25], however, is much faster and more dynamic. The disadvantage is that it can only be used with pre-trained objects, and the trained model must be stored on the device. Therefore, it is currently not suitable for automatically recognizing a moving object if it is not included in the installed model.

The situation is further complicated if several objects have to be tracked at the same time. Multiple Object Tracking (MOT) has gained significant attention in recent years, driven by advancements in computer vision and deep learning. Many solutions implement tracking using ORB key points [4, 20, 26, 27]. For example, in [4] a multi-2D object tracking solution is presented and ORB is used to match and associate key points extracted from consecutive RGB frames. The association of the ORB descriptors between the frames was improved with an algorithm that calculates the distance of the key point of the movement speed of the features, which makes it possible to filter out unrealistic deviations, thus verifying the accuracy of the association.

2.3 Multi-user and large-scale applications

In addition, if we assume multi-user systems, where the inputs of environment detection and comprehension come from different users and devices, additional delays are introduced which affect the user experience and require more complex synchronization methods. However, large-scale MR applications need to apply the "more eyes see more" rule to get much more information about the environment in order to enable e.g. global scenes and immersive interactions in that. Multi-user MR applications pose further challenges and it is worth noting that creating them is far from easy. One of the key problems to be solved is the synchronization of coordinate systems. In contrast to multiplayer computer games, where each player roams within a completely virtual world with known origin and clear coordinates of positions, in MR applications, the users move within the real physical world and each of them designates the starting point as their own origin when launching the application. Therefore, if we instruct the program to display an object at specific 3D coordinates, everyone will see it in a different location. Of course, there are several methods for synchronizing the coordinate systems, but none of them are perfect. One of these common techniques is the QR code or image recognition technique, when we place an image or QR code in the physical space that every user sees in the same location, allowing us to use its pose as the origin. The main issue of this solution is that devices may

not perfectly recognize the rotation of the images, and even just one degree of deviation away from the origin can cause significant differences in the system. The other common method is based on the matching of feature points, which can be used relatively well in small spaces, for example in a small room. However, since the problem can be traced back to the point cloud registration, if we want to use this technique in a larger space, the synchronization will either be inaccurate or take several seconds [17].

Another option invokes offloading and runs the SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) function in the edge cloud. It can be combined with jointly built and managed global maps, which can address the issue of coordinate system synchronization in multiplayer systems [19]. If several devices do this in a cooperative manner, this can also enable an environment interpretation where we get a detailed picture of the part of our environment that we do not have a direct view of. Thus, we can create a model of an object as a whole, even if we only have a view of the front side of it.

In multiplayer Extended Reality (XR) environments, network requirements play a crucial role in maintaining an immersive and synchronized experience. Achieving low-latency, high-bandwidth (in some cases), and reliable connections are essential to avoid lag and desynchronization, which would lead to a drastic decrease in the user experience. Key requirements for multiplayer XR is the low latency (typically below 20 ms) with the low jitter, but in case of remote rendering the high bandwidth (couple of tens of Mbps bitrate) is also important [2, 10]. Meeting these requirements is a huge challenge with today's mobile networks, so in many cases we (will) have to rely on B5G or 6G solutions [7, 21, 30].

3 Proposed architecture

Addressing the highlighted challenges, we have designed an edge cloud based system architecture for future MR applications supporting low-latency immersive interactions together with high visual quality. The proposed architecture is shown in Fig. 1. Central to the concept is the offloading of resource-intensive tasks to the edge cloud while the device executes lighter or delay-critical functions. By the end of the day, three different functionalities and related control loops shall be harmonized, which are denoted by different colors in the figure. The lower part (green) is responsible for object detection and tracking, the center elements (orange) correspond to the 3D simulation, while the upper section (blue) denotes components realizing remote rendering solutions. The main steps of the operation are the following: *i*) 3D environment in the simulation server is updated based on object detection/tracking information, *ii*) pose (position and orientation) of the HMD device is sent to the server, *iii*) a 2D image is rendered by the server based on its 3D view and sent to the device, and finally *iv*) the 2D image is warped and displayed. In this section, the main concepts and components of the architecture are detailed.

3.1 Object centric rendering

In the industry, there are already several remote rendering platforms. However, it can be observed that in each of these, the server sends an image and possibly its depth information to users, including all virtual objects. However, this solution has its drawbacks, particularly in managing movements. For example, if two objects

Figure 1: Our multi-user edge/cloud-based Mixed Reality platform

Figure 2: Lack of pixels in case of object movement

Figure 3: Lack of pixels in case of user movement

Figure 4: Processing time statistics of object detection and object tracking

move in opposite directions, and for some reason a frame does not arrive in time or is discarded, the system attempts to track what should be displayed to the user based on the information from the previous frames. However, as shown in Fig. 2, in such cases, not all pixels are available. Information is missing from the area marked with red dots in the system. Similarly, in cases where objects are stationary but overlap, a similar phenomenon can occur. For instance, if the user starts moving away from a virtual object in front of them, they should progressively see more parts of the objects behind the first one, but there is no information about these. Fig. 3 illustrates this scenario. These pixel losses not only degrade the user experience but also contribute to motion sickness.

Object centric rendering as defined by us, can provide a solution to these problems. In this case, we don't send only one image to the user about the scene, but we render an image for each object separately and display them on the client in the position of the object on a canvas. Thus, if an image is lost, the previous images contain the entire object, thereby avoiding pixel loss in the system.

In our prototype, only two objects are rendered remotely, with each client receiving two separate streaming channels. Of course, the question arises, if we render a separate image for each object and send the image to the clients separately, won't our traffic increase enormously? Of course, our traffic may increase, but not to a large extent. We have several optimization options. For example, it is not necessary to render all images in high resolution, since distant objects will be placed far away on a canvas anyway. We do not need to start a separate stream for each object, as this would put a significant load on the devices. We can copy several smaller images created by us into the memory area of a large image one after the other, so only one image needs to be encoded on the server and decoded on the client.

In addition, in many cases it is not necessary to render all objects remotely, since several applications use objects with a low polygon count, which the device can also render. Hence, a hybrid or split rendering approach can be applied [16, 18].

3.2 Latency hiding

Since we outsource several components, it's evident that there will be latency in the system, which we must try to conceal to avoid degrading the user experience. The warp itself is a well-established concept in virtual reality, aiming to ensure that the user sees the image corresponding to their current head pose. It is also crucial in MR applications supporting low-latency interactions.

Another important mechanism for hiding latency is prediction. In our system, we assume various movements, such as head motion and the motion of tracked objects, but we need to transmit these to the server and then to the clients. Consequently, the data would be outdated by the time it reaches the users. For instance, a virtual object attached to a moving object would always lag behind its actual motion. To solve this, we apply prediction algorithms in the system at the client and the server side to forecast the position of the moving object at the time of display, based on our current knowledge.

Offloading not only introduces latency into the system, but also jitter. In many cases, this causes a bigger problem than the delay itself, since if we experience very large jumps in the delay on the network, we will also see jumps and outages in the remote rendered stream and in updating object positions. A jitter buffer (which is a temporary storage to compensate for jitter in arrival times caused by network delays) can reduce it at the cost of extra delay. We can achieve a significantly better user experience if there are no frame drops in the system. However, too large jitter buffer can introduce a disturbingly high delay into the system, which also leads to a deterioration of the user experience. Therefore, finding the golden mean in choosing the jitter buffer size in a remote render system is a particular challenge and depends on the characteristics of the network and the specific use-case.

Object-centric rendering enables another latency-hiding technique when each object is handled separately, and the image and position associated with each object are sent via separate streams. It is evident that the rendering loop (blue arrow in Fig. 1), including rendering, encoding, sending, decoding, and displaying the image, is "slower" than the sending of position updates (orange arrow). By leveraging this, we can respond to movements faster than if we were using a fully remote rendering system. We can move the image associated with the object before the updated frames actually arrive, which provides roughly a 20-30 ms advantage, but this number also depends on the size of the jitter buffer. In practical terms, if a real toy car collides with a virtually remote-rendered ball, we can move the ball sooner than the rendered image showing the effect of the collision reaches the device. By these means, we can avoid visual inconsistencies in our use-case, where the car would be partially inside the ball without the ball moving yet.

3.3 Fast and slow paths

As Fig. 1 shows, there are several communication paths in our system, which usually differ in update frequency and message sending speed. In the detection and tracking part (marked by green color), the detection has been separated and only tracking runs locally. There are several reasons for this. First, the two components do not necessarily have to run together, since tracking does not require to know exactly what we are tracking, only the points to be tracked are

Figure 5: The remotely rendered MR car soccer game

needed. Second, object detection is a much more resource-intensive and slow process, thus outsourcing of that is quite straightforward. Fig. 4 presents a baseline measurement indicating the significant difference in runtime between the two components. Finally, due to the separation, the training data set of the detection algorithm or the object models can easily be replaced, extended or refined.

As tracking runs separately and it just needs to know which points to track, it is not necessary to continuously send an image to the object detection component. In our case, since we want to track a slowly moving toy car, we have found that sending one or a couple of images every second when the tracker loses the points to be tracked is enough. This route is therefore a slow path. In contrast, the object tracking result directly affects the user experience, so we have to run it with the highest possible frequency and forward the results to the simulation server as quickly as possible (which is 30 Hz in our system).

4 Our proof-of-concept prototype

To test the system components and validate our concept, we developed the outlined system and created a Mixed Reality game. A snapshot of the game is shown in Fig. 5. In this game, which resembles soccer, two users control real remote-controlled cars and use HoloLens 2 headsets to drive virtual balls into virtual goals. The developed multiplayer game supports two players who can compete against each other either in the same physical location or from two different remote locations. The game features pickup objects that, when collected, provide users with goalkeeper monsters as temporary assistance. The positions of the cars are continuously tracked by the environment detection and tracking system, and the data is sent to the game server. The application uses split rendering, so objects that need to appear as realistic as possible with high quality, like the soccer ball and monsters, are rendered remotely, while less important static objects like the goals and field elements are rendered locally. The implementation details of each component are explained in the following subsections.

4.1 Environment detection and tracking

The lower control loop with green boxes in Fig. 1 is the real-time environment detection service, which is split between the tracking

device and the cloud platform. On the one hand, the AI-based object detection is offloaded to the GPU-powered edge cloud and it performs the image classification on the received 2D images streamed from the client devices. On the other hand, the delay-sensitive tracking function is run locally e.g. on an iPhone (mobile AR) device. In our prototype, the tracking device receives updates from the object detector every second, while the tracking runs continuously (at 30 FPS in our setup). During the prototype development, an iPhone was utilized to determine its position using the ARKit library and to synchronize its coordinate system with the HoloLens by recognizing the QR code placed on the track. Subsequently, the iPhone was mounted on a fixed stand, eliminating any movement. This allowed for the deactivation of the SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) component, thereby reducing computational load and optimizing the system's runtime efficiency.

We send 1920x1440 resolution images to the object detection server at a rate of one frame per second using UDP streaming. On the server, we use deep learning image classification to determine the positions of the four corners of the toy car in the image. This information is then sent back to the object tracking device, which is an iPhone 13 Pro with LiDAR scanner in our case. The tracker device uses this data along with depth information collected by the LiDAR to calculate the 3D coordinates of the four points and tracks them with OpenCV. In each cycle, the tracker forms a pose data of the car from the updated four positions and transmits this to the simulation server.

4.2 Unity-based object-centric rendering

The server-side part of the upper two control loops was implemented in Unity 3D engine. The first part is the Simulation Server. It performs the physical calculation (such as collision), records the position of the players and also has a picture of the real environment by the green environment detection service. To handle a rapidly changing dynamic environment, the simulation server (regardless of the rendering loop) can process the environment detection information and send updates about the pose of virtual objects based on this, or predict the movements of objects in the game space based on past data. Thus, the simulation is as close to the actual state of reality as possible, and the image displayed on the HMD reacts more quickly to environment changes, which is of paramount importance when the virtual content is in close interaction with the environment (e.g.: a real moving object collides with a virtual ball).

The second loop is responsible for remote rendering (blue components in Fig. 1). This starts with the client device (HoloLens 2 headset in our prototype), which sends the head pose of the user to the server. HoloLens 2 also provides the user's hand-gesture and all the coordinates of their hand, which may be useful for another use-cases, but we are currently only using the head pose. Based on this, we update the position of the virtual cameras associated with the user and does the rendering. The images are delivered to the clients by a native C++ plugin consisting of a hardware based encoder (making use of Nvidia's NVCodec library) and our custom RTP streamer which transports the video streams. Note that, we update the position of the virtual cameras associated with the user, but not their rotation. According to object-centric guidelines the camera on the server side always aims at the virtual object and the

content is displayed on the client's canvas even if the user is not looking there. Hence, quick movements and viewport updates can also be handled.

At the client side, we have prepared a HoloLens 2 application with Unity that receives and displays the remote rendered images. A C++ plugin was created to receive and decode the image making use of AVCodec library with hardware support. It decodes the images into YUV format, so we create the final RGB images from the Y and UV layers using a Unity shader. In the application (Presenter module in Fig. 1), we display the decoded images on dedicated canvas where the effects of latency caused by the remote rendering is mitigated by applying our own warp algorithm, which is an image distortion mechanism before displaying the image and makes it more realistic (for further details, see Sec. 4.3).

4.3 Latency and jitter hiding

As we mentioned before, we can apply a special warp mechanism for latency hiding building on the object-centric rendering concept. When the image of the given object arrives on the clients, we display it to the user on a canvas. However, we do not turn this canvas towards the user's actual head position, but to the position to which the currently displayed image belongs. So we use a head position from the past. Thus, the user's viewing angle differs by a few degree and the user looks at the canvas at a bit flatter angle. The image seen by the user is therefore minimally distorted, however, sudden motions can be followed more smoothly.

Furthermore, the pose data sent to the simulation server is of course outdated data, because no matter how fast the tracker is, it works from past data. For this reason, we use a pose prediction to estimate where the object will be when our data reaches the client devices. This algorithm is currently based on simple curve fitting to historical data and its accuracy depends on the velocity and acceleration of the moving object. This simple method is suitable in context of the prototype application, but more sophisticated (e.g. AI-based) methods can be added later to handle other use-cases as well.

Optimally, the prediction time on the server will be very close to the users display time. Although this is a short amount of time, a fast-moving object can move significantly during this time. Normally this does not cause serious visible errors in the display, but when a virtual object is attached to the moving object, the display of the virtual object may show a visible lag. To mitigate this problem, we also implemented a local prediction algorithm on the clients, which creates a predicted pose for the planned display time based on the received data (Local object pose prediction component in Fig. 1).

If the network conditions require, for example due to background traffic, then it should be necessary to use a dejitter buffer on the client side in order to ensure a continuous stream. We will discuss the importance of this in Sec. 6.1.

5 Measurement environment

This section is devoted to our measurement environment, including the description of the academic Beyond 5G testbed and the deployment of our system.

Figure 6: The academic Beyond 5G network infrastructure

5.1 Beyond 5G test infrastructure

The Beyond 5G network (IMAGINE B5G @UPV), shown by Fig. 6, consists of three Radio Access Network (RAN) nodes, an Open5GS core [14], and a router interconnecting them. Two nodes operate in the n40 frequency band, while the third operates in the n78 frequency band. The core runs seven distinct User Plane Functions (UPFs) to serve User Equipment (UE). All UPFs are deployed on the same virtual machine (VM) with 16 GB of RAM and six CPUs. Three UPFs are configured to serve UEs connected to the n40 frequency band, another three serve the n78 frequency band, and the last one is shared among the two bands. The selection of the UPF is determined by the Data Network Name (DNN) chosen by the UE.

Network slicing is an essential feature of 5G/B5G systems where the physical network infrastructure is shared among logical networks comprising all of the required network resources from radio via transport to the core network in order to provide the defined end-to-end service quality for a given set of users/devices. Mapping DNNs to slices (and UPFs) is described in the core database. Each UPF uses a separate network interface (subinterface) to connect to the RAN data plane (N3 interface of the reference architecture), and the traffic separation is provided by VLAN tagging. This network setup enables the implementation of Quality of Service (QoS) through different mechanisms.

Some relevant QoS mechanisms are associated with the 5QI (5G QoS Identifier) parameter. 5QI is configured for each UE at the core level and is linked at the RAN level to the Scheduling Weight and Differentiated Services Code Point (DSCP) parameters, which can directly control the QoS of the UE. On the one hand, the Scheduling Weight influences the gNB (base station) MAC scheduler for uplink and downlink traffic, as well as the multiplexing of Data Radio Bearers (DRBs) for downlink traffic. This ensures that more radio resources are allocated for UEs with a higher scheduling weight. On the other hand, DSCP is an IP header field for traffic labeling. This

Figure 7: B5G deployment of our MR platform

label is tagged at the RAN based on the 5QI parameter. The router between the RAN and the core can read DSCP labels and apply policies accordingly. For instance, the router may set a maximum throughput value for a specific DSCP label, discarding excess traffic. In addition, the latency-sensitive components can be deployed to edge nodes close to the users. In order to provide an interface for configuring these network capabilities, CAPIF (Common API Framework for 3GPP Northbound APIs) was introduced by 3GPP Release 15 and was further evolved in subsequent releases (Beyond 5G). It is a key component providing a standardized way for applications to interact with the network to foster a wide range of innovative applications.

5.2 B5G deployment of the MR platform

Our system has been deployed to this Beyond 5G (B5G) network infrastructure. The integration and the mapping of the components are illustrated by Fig. 7. In this network, components associated with the edge/cloud platform are directly connected to the core network, while the HoloLens HMDs are connected to the access network using a Qualcomm Snapdragon X55 chipset (SDX55) based USB dongle. The iPhone 13 Pro, which is responsible for tracking, is equipped with specific 5G SIM card and connected via given B5G radio channels. Additionally, several traffic generator clients are deployed making use of Acer Predator 5G dongles. By these means, we can generate traffic and congestion in the radio access network, making the measurement scenarios more realistic. During the measurements, the average total traffic generated by the clients was 500 Mbps.

Connecting the HoloLens to the B5G network turned to be challenging. On the one hand, several dongles are not supported by HoloLens and the 5G connection cannot be established. On the other hand, we can opt for combined modem/router devices, such as Advantech ICR-4453 5G router or Siemens Scalance 5G modem. However, we can only use these modems with the HoloLens via WiFi, which introduces significant jitter to the system, thereby skewing the measurement results, or we have to connect the HoloLens through an Ethernet cable, requiring an additional conversion (Ethernet-to-USB-C adapter).

As a consequence, only the SDX55 chipset based 5G modem has allowed us to connect HoloLens HMDs directly to the B5G

Figure 8: Latency measurements

network via the USB-C port. Therefore, in the paper, we present the measurement results obtained with this 5G modem.

6 Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate the performance of our system in different scenarios. First, we examine the runtime of each component. Second, the results of the B5G experiments are summarized, including quantitative and qualitative (subjective) aspects as well.

6.1 Latency analysis of the components

We have developed a detailed measurement method for measuring the delays of each relevant software component in our system. The high-level setup is shown in Fig. 8a (which is a simplified version of the complex architecture plot presented earlier by Fig. 1). In order to be able to measure the latency on the paths through different devices, it is necessary to synchronize the clocks. For this, we use our own NTP client on all devices (HoloLens, iPhone) and they synchronize to the gameserver's clock.

Fig. 8b summarizes the average The different types of information (pose or frame) reach the user's display via different routes. The 1st bar (Frame path) describes the average latency until the frame is displayed on the HoloLens, which was made based on the environment detection's pose information. The 3rd bar (Pose path) shows the average latency until the pose information reaches the HoloLens from the environment detection. The components in Fig. 8a and Fig. 8b are marked with similar colors and represent the following elements: 1) the green part is the processing time of environment detection (including image retrieval from iPhone and object tracking based on the low-FPS detection feed); 2) the yellow part is the network transmission time between the iPhone and the gameserver; 3) the orange part is the server processing time (simulation time, object pose prediction, pose updates of the virtual objects); and here, the route splits. 4a) The gameserver sends the 3D car pose information directly to the HoloLens (orange part in Fig. 8b and orange arrow in Fig. 8a) and 4b) based on this information, the server updates the position of the virtual objects, renders the given frame, sends it to the client and the HoloLens present it to the user

(blue part in Fig. 8b and blue arrow in Fig. 8a). Here, we do not use a jitter buffer.

As one can see, the processing time of the object tracking is about 64 ms. This is mainly determined by the image retrieval from the iPhone. Unfortunately, the situation is even worse if SLAM is also enabled on the device (this is about an extra 40 ms), since we can request the image only after the local SLAM has processed it (part of ARKit in iPhone). This case is indicated by the faded bars (2nd bar for frame path and 4th bar for pose path) in Fig. 8b. However, if we turn off ARKit, we cannot move the phone (or any other tracker device) because the current pose of the tracking device is not known without the SLAM. The iPhone-Server transmission time is negligible (about 3 ms), and the server processing time is not high (about 10 ms). However, it is clearly visible that sending the image (about 37 ms) takes much more time than sending the pose to the HoloLens (about 14 ms). Here, the time until the main Unity thread processes the asynchronous messages received from environment tracking is also included.

As mentioned, the position data reaches client devices before the image. Thus, we can respond to movement-induced collisions faster using the object-centric approach compared to fully remote rendering systems. The approximately 20-25 ms response time difference is noticeable even to the naked eye.

The blue part shown in Fig. 8b can be further broken down as shown in Fig. 8c. This represents the average delay and the standard deviation of the rendering, encoder, network transmission, receiver side queue, decoder components and the display delay (reported by Unity). Rendering takes less than 2 ms, the hardware encoder (Nvidia NVEncode) and the network transmission time (RTP streamer) are about 8 ms and the hardware decoder on HoloLens side (AVCodec) finishes within 1-2 ms. The other two components (receiver queue and display delay) are primarily determined by the difference between the async functions (frame reception, decoding, display) and the main thread of Unity. This is greatly influenced by the frame rate of the Unity app running on HoloLens.

Figure 9: Average latency & jitter of remote rendered frames

6.2 Beyond 5G network experiments

Our B5G environment, providing extended capabilities and features for available 5G network, allows different scenarios to be measured. Here, we analyze the operation of our XR platform and the application in the B5G setup, reveal the impact of congestion in the network (radio access network) and evaluate mitigation techniques at the network level (slice prioritization) and at the application level (jitter buffer). All components were monitored but here we primarily focus on the remote-rendered video stream, because we found that it has the greatest impact on the user experience. Latency and jitter characteristics are analyzed in idle network and under high-traffic conditions, respectively. Then the impact of the prioritization of the video stream to HoloLens and the dynamic setting of the jitter buffer are investigated.

Fig. 9 summarizes the results of our measurements. The two yellow bars on the left show the basic setup (without priority) in idle and congested network, respectively. The average latency jumps by 2 ms but the jitter exhibits much more concerning characteristics and its value nearly quadruples. The purple bars represent scenarios with priority enabled (on slice including HoloLens). The increase in latency and jitter due to the network congestion is minimal, which means a significant improvement.

The detailed characteristics of the low-level data series are further analyzed. This is crucial, as we need to apply a completely different jitter buffer if the 8 ms jitter comes from many smaller spikes rather than fewer, larger latency spikes. Fig. 10 shows the detailed latency characteristics of the time series of the two different streams. It can be seen that, in the case without priority (blue line), there are 100-140 ms jumps, while with priority (orange line), the latency does not exceed 20 ms.

These large spikes can cause frame drops, significantly reducing the user experience. To counteract this, we apply a jitter buffer (discussed in Sec. 3.2), which transforms jitter (and frame drops) into additional latency. Our goal is to find the optimal trade-off that provides the best image quality (minimal drops) with the lowest possible latency. To achieve this, we can look at the time gaps between frames received on the HoloLens to figure out how often they were delayed. From this, we can calculate the percentage

Figure 10: Latency characteristic of received frames

Figure 11: Impact of jitter buffer size on frame drop rate

Figure 12: Rate of consecutive frame drops in terms of jitter buffer size w/ and w/o priority

of frame drops in the system, meaning the cases when the next frame does not arrive in time. In Fig. 11, we demonstrate how the

Figure 13: Subjective evaluation

percentage of dropped frames varies in terms of the size of the jitter buffer under heavy network traffic. This shows that, in prioritized scenarios, a jitter buffer of 20-30 ms is typically sufficient, causing only a 1-2 frame delay at a 60 Hz display rate. In non-prioritized scenarios, however, this buffer size requirement increases to 100-120 ms, resulting in a delay of up to 8 frames!

A single frame drop might slightly reduce video quality, but users probably will not notice if they are seeing 59 frames per second instead of 60. However, if multiple frame drops occur in a row, the resulting stutter in the video stream is more noticeable to the user. Hence, it is important to reveal how likely consecutive frame drops occur in the system. This is illustrated in Fig. 12. As shown, the probability of even two consecutive frame drops is lower in prioritized cases than the chance of four consecutive drops in non-prioritized setups.

Jitter differences are significant not only for frame transmission but also play a crucial role in position updates. Large jumps in position updates can lead to choppy object movement, which similarly degrades the user experience.

6.3 Subjective evaluation

We conducted a subjective test with 19 users (familiar with XR technologies) to evaluate the visual quality of the application, the response time of the car-ball collision, and the overall user experience. During the measurements, we prioritized the traffic of the HoloLenses over other network traffic without generating additional traffic on the network. During testing, two users played a five-minute match against each other at the same time, after which they evaluated the application. The ratings were on a scale from 1 to 5 (1 is lowest, 5 is highest quality). The test results are illustrated in Fig. 13. In terms of visual quality, the app received an average rating of 3.36, with scores ranging from 2 to 5. While some users gave higher ratings, several participants noted deficiencies in the graphical presentation. This could be due to the fact that, as revealed in the test, the vast majority of the testers regularly play video games, which obviously provide a higher visual experience than the app we developed.

The response time of the car-ball collision was also evaluated by users, receiving an average score of 3.0, with values ranging between 1 and 4. Based on the relatively low average score, many users found the delay in the ball's movement unsatisfactory. This was unfortunately expected, as we measured that the car's movement becomes noticeable on the HoloLens after approximately 100 ms, which is a delay that all users can perceive. In the future, we plan to replace the iPhone with a faster device with lower image access times to significantly improve this metric.

The overall user experience had an average rating of 4.0, with scores ranging from 2 to 5, indicating that, on average, we were able to provide a good user experience to the participants.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we have proposed a novel edge cloud based architecture answering different challenges of future remote-rendered MR applications. The most critical feature/aspect we have addressed is the low-latency immersive interaction. This requires several capabilities and operation characteristics from the underlying infrastructure, including edge cloud, networks and devices. In order to meet the visual fidelity goal, offloading to edge cloud infrastructure is crucial, but as a result, the introduced additional latency has to be managed or mitigated by other novel techniques. By the end of the day, the remote rendering, 3D simulation and environment detection control loops have to be harmonized in an efficient way.

To validate our concepts, a proof-of-concept prototype together with a challenging MR application have been delivered and experiments in a Beyond 5G network infrastructure were conducted. We have analyzed the operation of our XR platform and the application in different scenarios, revealed the impact of congestion in the radio access network and evaluated mitigation techniques at the network level (slice prioritization) and at the application level (dimensioning of a jitter buffer).

We found that the remote-rendered video stream has the greatest impact on the user experience. The results show that the latency and jitter characteristics can be managed efficiently together by a network-level control mechanism (prioritizing network slices including the HMDs) and a dynamic jitter buffer at the application-level. Furthermore, we plan to supplement the system with dynamic bit-rate control based on network congestion prediction.

Besides, the quality of the user experience has also been assessed via real-life experiments conducted as part of a student competition. The overall user experience can be summarized as good, however, the visual quality and the response time of physical-virtual interactions need further improvement which is part of our future work.

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References

- [1] Narmeen N. Al-Hiyari and Shaidah S. Jusoh. 2021. Healthcare Training Application: 3D First Aid Virtual Reality. In *International Conference on Data Science, E-Learning and Information Systems 2021 (DATA'21)*. Association for Computing Machinery, 107–116. doi:10.1145/3460620.3460741
- [2] Fredrik Alriksson, Oskar Drugge, Anders Furuskär, Jonas Kronander, Jose Luis Pradas, Ying Sun, et al. 2023. Future network requirements for extended reality applications. *Ericsson Technology Review* 2023, 4 (2023), 2–12.
- [3] Apple. 2025. ARKit. <https://developer.apple.com/augmented-reality/arkit/>.
- [4] Jieyu Chen, Zhenghao Xi, Junxin Lu, and Jingjing Ji. 2022. Multi-object tracking based on network flow model and ORB feature. *Applied Intelligence* 52, 11 (Sept. 2022), 12282–12300. doi:10.1007/s10489-021-03042-6
- [5] Hung-Lin Chi, Shih-Chung Kang, and Xiangyu Wang. 2013. Research trends and opportunities of augmented reality applications in architecture, engineering, and construction. *Automation in Construction* 33 (Aug. 2013), 116–122. doi:10.1016/j.autcon.2012.12.017
- [6] Archi Dasgupta, Mark Manuel, Rifat Sabbir Mansur, Nabil Nowak, and Denis Gračanin. 2020. Towards Real Time Object Recognition For Context Awareness in Mixed Reality: A Machine Learning Approach. In *2020 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)*. 262–268. doi:10.1109/VRW50115.2020.00054
- [7] Mohammed S. Elbamby, Cristina Perfecto, Mehdi Bennis, and Klaus Doppler. 2018. Toward Low-Latency and Ultra-Reliable Virtual Reality. *IEEE Network* 32, 2 (2018), 78–84. doi:10.1109/MNET.2018.1700268
- [8] Yalda Ghasemi, Heejin Jeong, Sung Ho Choi, Kyeong-Beom Park, and Jae Yeol Lee. 2022. Deep learning-based object detection in augmented reality: A systematic review. *Computers in Industry* 139 (2022), 103661. doi:10.1016/j.compind.2022.103661
- [9] Tariq Masood and Johannes Egger. 2019. Augmented reality in support of Industry 4.0—Implementation challenges and success factors. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* 58 (2019), 181–195. doi:10.1016/j.rcim.2019.02.003
- [10] Microsoft. 2024. Network requirements. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/remote-rendering/reference/network-requirements>.
- [11] Microsoft. 2025. Azure Remote Rendering. <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/products/remote-rendering>.
- [12] Reza Moezzi, David Krmarik, Jindřich Čyrus, Haythem Bahri, and Jan Koci. 2022. Object Detection Using Microsoft HoloLens by a Single Forward Propagation CNN. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Intelligent Vision and Computing (ICIVC 2021)*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 507–517.
- [13] Nvidia. 2025. CloudXR. <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/design-visualization/solutions/cloud-xr/>.
- [14] Open5GS. 2024. Open5GS. <https://github.com/open5gs>.
- [15] Psyonix. 2024. RocketLeague. <https://www.rocketleague.com/en>.
- [16] Qualcomm. 2018. Boundless XR in a new era of distributed computing. <https://www.qualcomm.com/news/onq/2018/09/boundless-xr-new-era-distributed-computing>.
- [17] Shu Gan Raobo Li, Xiping Yuan and Rui Bi. 2024. A robust correspondence-based registration method for large-scale outdoor point cloud. *International Journal of Digital Earth* 17, 1 (2024), 2407943. doi:10.1080/17538947.2024.2407943 arXiv:<https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2024.2407943>
- [18] Jangwoo Son, Serhan Gül, Gurdeep Singh Bhullar, et al. 2020. Split Rendering for Mixed Reality: Interactive Volumetric Video in Action. In *SIGGRAPH Asia 2020 XR*. New York, NY, USA. doi:10.1145/3415256.3421491
- [19] Balázs Sonkoly, Bálint György Nagy, János Dóka, Zsófia Kecskés-Solymosi, János Czentye, Bence Formanek, Dávid Jocho, and Balázs Péter Gerő. 2023. Towards an Edge Cloud Based Coordination Platform for Multi-User AR Applications Built on Open-Source SLAMs. In *NOMS 2023-2023 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium*. 1–6. doi:10.1109/NOMS56928.2023.10154295
- [20] Daniel Stadler and Jürgen Beyerer. 2022. BYTEv2: Associating more detection boxes under occlusion for improved multi-person tracking. In *International Conference on Pattern Recognition*. Springer, 79–94.
- [21] Jakob Struye, Sam Van Damme, Nabeel Nisar Bhat, Arno Troch, Barend Van Liempd, Hany Assasa, Filip Lemic, Jeroen Famaey, and Maria Torres Vega. 2024. Toward Interactive Multi-User Extended Reality Using Millimeter-Wave Networking. *IEEE Communications Magazine* 62, 8 (2024), 54–60. doi:10.1109/MCOM.001.2300804
- [22] Bruce H. Thomas. 2012. A survey of visual, mixed, and augmented reality gaming. *Computers in Entertainment* 10, 1 (Oct. 2012), 1–33. doi:10.1145/2381876.2381879
- [23] Unity. 2025. Barracuda. <https://docs.unity3d.com/Packages/com.unity.barracuda@3.0/manual/>.
- [24] J. M. P. van Waveren. 2016. The asynchronous time warp for virtual reality on consumer hardware. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM Conference on Virtual Reality Software and Technology (Munich, Germany) (VRST '16)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 37–46. doi:10.1145/2993369.2993375
- [25] Viometry. 2024. VisionLib. <https://visionlib.com/>.
- [26] Shuang Wu, Yawen Fan, Shibao Zheng, and Hua Yang. 2012. Object tracking based on ORB and temporal-spatial constraint. In *2012 IEEE Fifth International Conference on Advanced Computational Intelligence (ICACI)*. IEEE, 597–600.
- [27] Xuefeng Xie and Hefeng Wu. 2012. ORB tracking via random model and sample consensus. In *2012 5th International Congress on Image and Signal Processing*. IEEE, 113–117.
- [28] Yingen Xiong and Christopher Peri. 2021. Space-Warp with Depth Propagation in XR Applications. In *2021 IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia (ISM)*. 50–57. doi:10.1109/ISM52913.2021.00017
- [29] Vinay Yadhav, Andrew Williams, Ondrej Smid, Jimmy Kjällman, Raihan Islam, Joacim Halén, and Wolfgang John. 2024. Benefits of Dynamic Computational Offloading for Mobile Devices. In *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Cloud Computing and Services Science - Volume 1: CLOSER, INSTICC, SciTePress*, 265–276. doi:10.5220/0012719800003711
- [30] Zhehui Zhang, Shu Shi, Varun Gupta, and Rittwik Jana. 2019. Analysis of cellular network latency for edge-based remote rendering streaming applications. In *Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2019 Workshop on Networking for Emerging Applications and Technologies*. 8–14.